

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Senataxin (UniProt ID: Q7Z333) for use in western blot

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Abstract

Senataxin is an RNA/DNA helicase implicated in genome integrity maintenance, RNA metabolism regulation and DNA damage control in the cell. Here we have characterized eleven Senataxin commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q7Z333, *SETX*, Senataxin, Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 4 protein, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot

Introduction

Senataxin is a 2677 amino acid protein encoded by the *SETX* gene. This protein contains an N-terminal protein-protein interaction domain, a conserved C-terminal DEAD-box helicase domain and a nuclear localization signal (1). Senataxin plays important roles in genome integrity maintenance, RNA metabolism regulation and DNA damage response and repair (2). Mutations in the *SETX* gene are associated with the autosomal dominant Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis type 4 and other neurodegenerative diseases (2).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (3). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (3). Here we characterized eleven commercial Senataxin antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Senataxin properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (4) and in Table 4 of this data note (3).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (5, 6). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (7). The RKO cell line expresses the *SETX* transcript at $5.2 \log_2$ TPM+1. A *SETX* KO RKO cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the RKO line does not carry mutations in the *SETX* gene that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

To screen the eleven antibodies by western blot, WT and *SETX* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all Senataxin antibodies in parallel (Figure 1). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Senataxin were identified.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Senataxin antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Senataxin, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Senataxin experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, the same antibody clones are donated by 2-3 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (3). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (8, 9). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

RKO WT and *SETX* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. HiMark™ Pre-stained Protein Standard (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number LC5699) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MOPS SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000102), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Data availability*Underlying data*

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-2577	CVCL_0504	RKO	WT
Abcam	-	-	RKO	<i>SETX</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Senataxin antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab220827	GR3296105-10	AB_2818949	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.600	IF
Abcam	ab243904**	GR3256312-7	AB_2893218	recombinant mono	BLR050F	rabbit	NA	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab300439**	GR3452849-3	AB_3105947	recombinant mono	EPR24137-74	rabbit	0.528	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NB100-57542	A3	AB_922411	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-14676**	2	AB_3597798	recombinant mono	BLR050F	rabbit	NA	Wb, IP, FlowCyt
Cell Signaling Technology	83407**	1	AB_3095740	recombinant mono	E9Z9F	rabbit	0.935	Wb
Proteintech	13837-1-AP	00004761	AB_3085425	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.350	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-44293**	ZF4352702	AB_2926423	recombinant mono	BLR050F	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-54979	XA3464112	AB_2647169	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.200	IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-66071	XA3464117B	AB_2663839	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.600	IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-72986	WL3464911	AB_2718840	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP, IF

IF= immunofluorescence; Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot

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Figure 1:
Senataxin antibody screening
by western in RKO cells

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Senataxin antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of RKO WT and *SETX* KO were prepared, and 50 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Senataxin antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab220827 at 1/500, ab243904** at 1/500, ab300439** at 1/500, NB100-57542 at 1/2000, NBP3-14676** at 1/500, 83407** at 1/500, 13837-1-AP at 1/500, MA5-44293** at 1/500, PA5-54979 at 1/500, PA5-66071 at 1/500, and PA5-72986 at 1/500. Predicted band size: 302.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.